

Building a Framework for Arabic Ontology Learning

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Abstract

This paper presents the ArOntoLearn a Framework for Arabic Ontology learning from textual resources. Supporting Arabic language and using domain knowledge or previous knowledge in the learning process are the main features of our framework, besides it represents the learned ontology in Probabilistic Ontology Model (POM), which can be translated into any knowledge representation formalism, and implements data-driven change discovery, therefore it updates the POM according to the corpus changes only, and allows user to trace the evolution of the ontology with respect to the changes in the underlying corpus. Our framework analyses Arabic textual resources, and matches them to Arabic Lexico-syntactic patterns in order to learn new Concepts and Relations.

Keywords: Ontologies, Ontology Learning, Knowledge Acquisition, Arabic Natural Language Processing.

Introduction

Since Ontologies provide a shared understanding of a domain of interest, they became the key technology of modern knowledge based systems: natural language processing, information retrieval and the Semantic Web. Since building ontology for a huge amount of data is a difficult and time consuming task, several ontology learning frameworks have been designed and implemented in the last decade.

The Mo'k workbench [1], for instance, basically relies on unsupervised machine learning methods to induce concept hierarchies from text collections.

OntoLT [2] is ontology learning plug-in for the Protege ontology editor. It is targeted more at end users and heavily relies on linguistic analysis. It basically makes use of the internal structure of noun phrases to drive ontology knowledge from texts.

The OntoLearn [3] framework by Velardi et al. focuses on the word sense disambiguation problem, presents a novel algorithm called SSI relying on the structure of the general ontology for this purpose.

TextToOnto [4] framework is implementing a variety of algorithms for diverse ontology learning subtasks. In particular, it implements diverse relevance measures for term extraction, different algorithms for taxonomy constructions as well as techniques for learning relations between concepts.

Text2onto [5] is a new version from textToOnto. It presented Preliminary Ontology Model provided with probability, and it relay on data-driven change discovery and NLP techniques.

All mentioned frameworks do not support Arabic language, and they do not use domain knowledge or previous knowledge such as assistant ontology. In this paper, we will present our framework which overcomes these deficient points by using Arabic Lexico-syntactic patterns and semantic annotator, which is based on a novel idea of using domain or previous knowledge in the traceable incremental ontology learning process. Supporting Arabic language is not that easy task because current linguistic analysis tools are not efficient enough

to process unvocalized Arabic corpuses that rarely contain appropriate punctuation, so we tried to build a flexible and freely configured framework whereas any linguistic analysis tool can be replaced by more sophisticated one whenever it is available.

This paper is structured as follows: in the first section we will describe the System Architecture which explains usage scenario and the system unit's interaction. These units will be detailed in the next three sections: The Probabilistic Ontology Model, Arabic Natural Language Processing, and Algorithms Controller. Some experimental results are presented in the Results and Discussion section. Conclusions and future work appear in final section.

System Architecture

The architecture of ArOntoLearn is divided into three units: Probabilistic Ontology Model POM, Algorithms Controller, and Arabic NLP tools (see figure 1).

Fig 1. Architecture of ArOntoLearn

POM stores the results of the different ontology learning algorithms, which are initialized by the Algorithms Controller, the purpose of which is to trigger the linguistic preprocessing of the data, execute the ontology learning algorithms in the appropriate order and apply the algorithms change requests to the POM. The fact that none of the algorithms has the permission of directly manipulating the POM guarantees maximum transparency and allows for the flexible composition of arbitrarily complex algorithm.

The execution of each algorithm consists of three phases: (i) in the notification phase, the algorithm learns about recent changes to the corpus, (ii) in the computation phase, these changes are mapped to changes with respect to the reference repository, which contains the pointers to all occurrences of the concept, (iii) in the result generation phase, request for POM changes are generated from the updated content of the reference repository.

Arabic Natural Language Processing NLP Unit is based on the GATE framework [6]. Our choice of GATE is based on two facts: its flexibility with respect to the set of linguistic algorithms used, and presenting Java Annotation Patterns Engine (JAPE) which provides finite state transduction over annotation based on regular expressions that gives flexible modeling and developing of Lexico-syntactic Patterns.

The Probabilistic Ontology Model

Probabilistic Ontology Model (POM) is presented by text2onto [5] framework as collection of instantiated modeling primitives which are independent of a concrete ontology representation language. The benefits of POM are twofold. On the one hand, adding new primitives does not

imply changing the underlying framework thus making it flexible and extensible. On the other hand, it can be translated into various ontology representation languages such as OWL and RDF. The modeling primitives we use in ArOntoLearn are:

- i. Concepts.
- ii. Instances.
- iii. Concept inheritance (subclass-of).
- iv. Concept instantiation (instance-of).

POM is not probabilistic in a mathematical sense, but because every instantiated modeling primitive gets assigned a value indicating how certain algorithm in question is about the existence of the corresponding instance. The purpose of these ‘probabilities’ is to facilitate the user interaction by allowing him to filter the POM and thereby select only a number of relevant instances of modeling primitives. Each POM change has references to the underlying corpus changes, that is, why the user can trace the evolution of the ontology with respect to the changes in the underlying corpus.

Arabic Natural Language Processing

Our Natural Language Processing unit is based on GATE framework which is very flexible and can be freely configured by replacing existing algorithms or adding new ones such as a deep parser if required, another advantage of using GATE is the ability of using existing Arabic linguistics analyzers.

Fig 2. Gate Pipeline Application

The Gate pipeline Application we used starts by Arabic tokenization and sentence splitting. The resulting annotation set serves as input for an Arabic Morphological Analyzer and POS-Tagger [7] which assigns appropriate morphological and POS tags to all tokens, such as (token=‘الطفولة’, POS-tag=‘common_noun’, root=‘طفل’, pattern=‘الفعولة’, stem=‘طفولة’, stem pattern=‘فعولة’). The resulting annotation set will serve as input for an Arabic Syntactical Analyzer [8] which will assign appropriate syntactic categories to all tokens and construct the syntactical trees of each sentence. For example, the sentence ‘دمشق هي العاصمة السورية’ will produce the annotations in the figure 3, where ‘دمشق’ and ‘هي’ are Proper noun phrase (NPP), and they construct a Noun Phrase (NP).

Fig 3. Syntactical Analyzer Annotations

Then, by using an assistant ontology such as Arabic WordNet (AWN) [11], which represents previous or domain knowledge in order to keep the result in the same domain and to get more accuracy, a Semantic Annotator will find and annotate all known concepts in the texts to get benefits from the knowledge we already had. For example (‘الجمهورية العربية السورية’) will be annotated by the concept ‘Syria’ or super-concept ‘country’).

according to relation type and elements, and we used AWN [11] lexical ontology to search for the relation, if it's found then the confidence will be 1 else it'll be 0.

Results and discussion

To evaluate the quality of the ontology learning results we tested our system on texts selected from Arabic Wikipedia. We have selected about 125 documents in the domain of countries and cities. We used Arabic WordNet as assistant ontology. We have established 15 Lexico-syntactic patterns (5 for instance-of relations, 10 for subclass-of relations). Our test focused on the instance-of relation. Since applying Stanford Syntactic Parser on Arabic sentences requires that these sentences are well formed and this are not the case Arabic Wikipedia documents, we have performed two tests: (i) by using Stanford Syntactic Parser on a limited number of sentences (34 sentences), (ii) by using only Arabic Morphological Analyzer, without Stanford Syntactic Parser on the whole corpus (12779 sentences) (see Table 1). We divided the results according to a relation confidence threshold that we have assigned the value 0.5. The results were as following:

i. Using Morphological Analyzer:

The number of relations with confidence more or equals 0.5 is 68. After the manual verification of these relations we found that, there are 26 true instance-of relation and 42 false instance-of relation.

The number of relations with confidence less than 0.5 is 40. After the manual verification of these relations we found that, there are 28 true instance-of relation and 12 false instance-of relation.

The precision of the results of this test is 0.5.

ii. Using Stanford Syntactic Parser:

The number of relations with confidence more or equals 0.5 is 10. After the manual verification of these relations we found that, there are 8 true instance-of relation and 2 false instance-of relation.

The number of relations with confidence less than 0.5 is 2. After the manual verification of these relations we found that, there are 2 true instance-of relation and none false instance-of relation.

The precision of the results of this test is 0.83.

Table 1: Results

	Sentences	≥ 0.5	True	False	< 0.5	True	False
Morphological	12779	68	26	42	40	28	12
Syntactical	34	10	8	2	2	2	0

We remarked that using Stanford Syntactic Parser has increased the precision of the results, because we could use the syntactic annotations of the sentences in the Lexico-syntactic patterns. Unfortunately we could not apply Stanford Syntactic Parser on the whole corpus, because it requires that the sentences are well formed and with appropriate punctuations.

Conclusion and Future Work

We have developed a framework for incremental ontology learning, using Arabic natural language processing, machine learning and text mining techniques, in order to extract ontology from Arabic textual resources. The novel aspects about our framework are: (i) the flexibility with respect to use other Arabic linguistic analyzers, and add new Lexico-syntactic patterns to reach more accuracy, (ii) the independence of a concrete ontology representation

language, (iii) benefits from the previous knowledge by using an assistant ontology, (iv) using the probability for capturing uncertainty and enhancing user interaction, (v) the integration of data-driven change discovery strategies increasing the efficiency of the system, as well as the traceability of the learned ontology with respect to changes in the corpus, making the whole process more transparent.

In the future, we intend to develop more Arabic Lexico-syntactic patterns to involve more relations and sentence forms. We can extend the POM with more taxonomic and non taxonomic relations. In view of increasing the precision of the system, we can replace existing Arabic morphological and syntactical analyzer with more accurate ones, and add an Arabic lemmetizer. We can use machine learning and text mining techniques in our algorithms used for extracting modeling primitives.

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